

PRINCIPLES OF FORMING TEACHER COMPETENCE THROUGH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotatoin.

In this article, the principles of using innovative technologies, i.e., digital technologies and electronic educational resources, in the formation of professional competences of pedagogues are presented.

Key words.

innovation, professional, competence, competence, pedagogical-psychological, communication, initiative, technology.

Pedagogical innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the educational process and the activities of teachers and students, their implementation is based on the full use of interactive methods. Interactive methods are methods of pedagogical influence that are an integral part of the educational content. The uniqueness of the methods is that they are implemented only through the interaction of the teacher and students.

The effectiveness of pedagogical technology depends on the technology chosen to achieve a guaranteed result, the joint choice of the teacher and the learner, that is, every educational technology used in the educational process can be organized to achieve the target guaranteed result. If pedagogues can think independently, work creatively, research, analyze, make their own conclusions, evaluate themselves and create opportunities and conditions for such activities, this will affect the quality of education.

Pedagogical technology in the educational process is an individual process, which is a purposeful, pre-planned and guaranteed pedagogical process based on educational needs. The choice of technology to achieve the goal remains at the discretion of the educator and the learner, since the main goal of both parties is to achieve a specific result. It is up to the learner to choose the technology to be used

depends on the level of knowledge. At the same time, the educational process must be developed in advance, in which the pedagogue takes into account the specific characteristics of the subject, the existing material and technical base, the tools of information and communication technologies, and most importantly, the capabilities and needs of learners and their ability to organize joint activities need. As a result, a guaranteed result is achieved.

The teacher must design the lesson process to know and demonstrate each lesson as a whole. In this case, it is important for the pedagogue to make a technological map of the lesson. Creating such a technological map is not easy, because it requires the pedagogue to know specific methods, pedagogical and digital technologies. The pleasure of each lesson depends on the technological map of the lesson, carefully thought out in advance.

In the development of professional competence of the pedagogue, it means the ability of the pedagogue to make clear decisions in problem situations, to create problematic tasks based on interdisciplinary interdependence, and to apply them in the educational environment. Ensuring the quality of teaching, interdisciplinary coherence and continuity in the acquisition of fundamental, in particular, pedagogical knowledge, the practical interaction of pedagogical sciences with humanitarian, socio-economic, mathematical and natural sciences, as well as general professional and special sciences scientific justification of aspects is required. Therefore, in order to develop the professional competence of the pedagogue, the use of high theoretical and practical, innovative pedagogical technologies, participation in innovative educational programs, being responsible for the full implementation of the process, organizing control of the knowledge, skills and qualifications of learners, preparing them for practical application of knowledge and innovative work control, creating a basis for educational and methodological equipment; scientific method of the educational institution it was considered necessary to participate in the activities, respect the rights and freedom of students.

Professional competence of a teacher is manifested in all aspects of pedagogical activity: professional and methodical activities, daily relationships, and personal development. However, there are still enough problems in developing the professional competence of today's pedagogues. Improvement, deepening and qualification of pedagogues' professional-methodical knowledge is revealed as an important factor in solving the problem. Also, the professional competence of pedagogues is reflected in their ability to be active in professional and social relations, to show their personal qualities as a perfect person.

It is necessary to determine the conditions for the creation of innovative pedagogical approaches, which are a necessary tool for the development of the professional competence of teachers, as follows:

- knowledge is given in various forms in a systematic, interdisciplinary and generalized form as a product of research and thinking activities, innovation process;

- the pedagogue appears as a "manager", "partner", takes the position of cooperation, freely influencing, helping, encouraging, paying attention to the personal initiatives of the learner;

- directed to the active cooperation of the pedagogue with the learner, to create an environment of mutual support and mutual responsibility;

- conditions are created for students to master various forms of interpersonal relations and communication, cooperation and innovation through group forms of organizing the educational process;

- abandoning the assessment of conformity to a predetermined pattern of actions and behaviors. Therefore, there are several stages in the development of professional competence based on personal involvement in social activities and an innovative approach, each of which is closely related to the others. The essence of interdependence can be both organic and reverse sequence.

The educational process is aimed at the development of professional competence, comprehensive mastering of knowledge and practical methods of activity that ensure the success of the pedagogue in the main areas of his activities, both for his personal interests and for the interests of society.

The maximum use of digital technologies and e-learning resources is important in developing the professional competence of teachers. In addition to educational and didactic materials, visual aids can also be included. They facilitate the creation of general and comprehensive ideas. In addition, audiovisual tools that form visual images create an all-round realistic view of technological processes and functions. Thematic tools allow you to record and save images and texts. These include whiteboards, flipcharts, projectors (cameras) and computers. At the same time, he should be able to independently solve technical problems that arise when using technical tools. Educational materials are used simultaneously as didactic materials, that is, for teaching and learning. If educational and didactic materials are not enough, then they should be selected by the teacher and prepared according to the purpose of theoretical or practical training.

In the educational process, positive activities such as analytical activity, foresight and design, which are consistently implemented by the pedagogue and

end with diagnostics, are demonstrated. Diagnostics, forecasting and design are an indispensable trinity for solving any pedagogical task. The purpose of the project is reflected in advance on paper in the form of a calendar plan, a brief written statement. Effective solving of strategic, tactical and operational tasks depends on the quality of the training process. Designing is a general strategy that reflects the social and pedagogical process of education. Curricula, textbooks, guidelines and other textbooks serve as an important resource in the design of the subject of professional competence.

Improvement of the curriculum in the application of innovative approaches and new methods in the educational process, creation of textbooks and training manuals in accordance with modern requirements, achievement of a single goal in accordance with the theoretical and practical characteristics of the curriculum, and the availability of pedagogical conditions have a strong impact on the development of the professional competence of the pedagogue.

Another factor in the effective use of methods in the educational process is the ability to pre-design a specific, complex educational process, diagnose the theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students, and predict the success of achieving educational goals.

The teacher, depending on the existing educational process, looks for positive changes by exerting various pedagogical influences on finding the necessary point (critical point) based on the needs of each learner. This requires a pedagogical understanding of the learner's direction and level of activity in the educational process.

In conclusion, it is known that the professional competence of pedagogues is measured by their professionalism, their activeness in professional and social activities, the ability to demonstrate the quality and efficiency of education, and also external factors, a free academic environment, and learners who are eager for knowledge are needed for a pedagogue to demonstrate his potential.

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